

E-PORTFOLIO: BEST PRACTICE FOR DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPREHENSION SKILL

Aytimbetova U.T.

Phd doctorant of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

E-mail: ulbiykeaytimbetova537@gmail.com

Abstract: The most information is perceived by listening, thus it is important to develop particularly foreign language learners. It is known that any learner is to be bored when he/she listens more. Thus, it needs an effective way of teaching to improve students' listening comprehension skill. The present study investigates using e-portfolios in improving listening skill of university students and examines the effectiveness of the use of e-portfolios in the teaching of listening by observing students' listening in the classroom.

Keyword: listening comprehension skill, e-portfolio, EFL students.

Introduction. It is known that any learner can communicate by listening, without it communication can not be. Understanding foreign language by listening demands the learners to be aware of grammatical structures and have a lexical resource. Thus, in the process of listening, it demands to the learner to be able to analyze and listen more. Clearly, it is time-consuming and more tedious for language learners listening any information more times. It is intended that most people have a desire to use digital learning technologies, in addition digital learning technologies is a part of their life. From these perspectives, using electronic portfolios for developing listening comprehension can motivate learner to listen to authentic materials in audio and video formats, real conversations, podcast and Ted talk applications, songs, interactive listening exercises. In fact, most students write a blog on the internet. Thus, by completing their portfolios in Google sites and sharing and comparing them with their peers and evaluating by their teachers, learners can spend their time more interesting and improve their listening comprehension skill. The research shows that e-portfolios not only gives motivation but also develop listening skill at the same time, so that EFL students can analyze their understanding of different speeches, accents, intonation, stress and so on when they listen to native speakers' speech by completing e-portfolios.

Thus, this study was conducted to investigate the use of e-portfolio for students of high education in the teaching of listening. Particularly, the study examines listening practices commonly utilized by EFL teachers to teach listening skills for university students in EFL classrooms. In this modern life, the need is very high to use digital learning technologies. The new generations of students have a high level of technology literacy. Hence, it is important to investigate the teachers' perception on the use of e-portfolio in the teaching of listening classrooms.

Literature review. Listening comprehension is a crucial skill in language learning, as highlighted by in the language laboratory setting [5]. Moulic emphasized the importance of effective listening skills and the challenges faced by technical undergraduate learners in improving their listening skills [3].

By incorporating video artifacts into e-portfolios, teachers were able to engage in reflective practices that supported inquiry into their classroom experiences. Research has also explored the potential of e-portfolios for promoting independent learning skills among students[2].

Insights from this research shed light on how e-portfolios can be used to foster independent learning across different educational settings. Furthermore, studies have investigated the impact of e-portfolios on self-regulated learning skills [1].

By implementing e-portfolio tools, educators can help students enhance their ability to monitor and regulate their own learning processes. In the context of technology acceptance, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been used to examine students' behavioral intention to use e-portfolio systems [6]. The implementation of e-portfolios supported by Lesson Study showed promising results in improving students' understanding of the subject matter, as discussed by [4].

Based on these ideas, e-portfolio was viewed as an effective tool in teaching listening as it gives students engagement to do a variety of listening tasks.

Research methods. This study employed a qualitative research design in the form of a descriptive case study. The study focused on students from higher educational institutions, specifically those with an intermediate level of English proficiency. Data was gathered through non-participant observation, wherein the researcher solely observed the teaching and learning processes without direct involvement. To obtain the data related to the use of e-portfolio in developing listening, students' listening was taken to investigate their listening ability since the use of e-portfolio was expected to help students to be motivated and do listening tasks based on real listening materials based on structure and language features.

Analysis and result. This research aimed to explore the implementation of e-portfolios in enhancing the listening skills of higher education students. Based on the findings and subsequent discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn.

The major conclusion of the study is that the use of e-portfolio in enhancing listening is successfully applied in some ways. Students can easily access e-portfolio and can practice, do assignments send to the teacher and also they can improve their listening skills self-study at home. The most important is that they can be motivated and engaged to improve listening comprehension skill.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that e-portfolio for teaching listening affects a better result of listening performance for students of high education.

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